

QUESTIONNAIRE

FAIRWISH USER TEMPLATE for sample IGSN REGISTRATION

Can also be filled out online at:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScMzDYLBP3rsgg3xONaMNxJStdxvNiQXH8A0I3NJ_tHelQYGg/viewform

USER TEMPLATE

- What was the Ease of Use you experienced with the FAIRWISH template?

Extremely easy

Somewhat easy

Neutral

Somewhat difficult

Extremely difficult

- If it was difficult: where were the main difficulties?

- It was well explained how to use the template (Sheet "HowTo")

Strongly agree

Somewhat agree

Neutral

Somewhat disagree

Strongly disagree

- If you disagree: What did you not understand?

- The setup of the “Guide” was clear to you

Strongly agree

Somewhat agree

Neutral

Somewhat disagree

Strongly disagree

- If you disagree: what was your main difficulty?

SAMPLE METADATA INPUT

- For which kind of samples (sample type and material) did you fill out the template?

- The variables for sample description were well described (Sheet "Guide")

Strongly agree

Somewhat agree

Neutral

Somewhat disagree

Strongly disagree

- If you disagree: which variables were particularly difficult to understand?

- Did you find all variables which are necessary to describe your samples?

Absolutely

Mainly

Not at all

- If not: which important variables to describe your samples are missing?

- What was the Ease of Use you experienced with the controlled vocabularies?

Extremely easy

Somewhat easy

Neutral

Somewhat difficult

Extremely difficult

- If it was difficult: where were the main difficulties and what would have helped you to make it easy?

- Were controlled vocabulary terms sufficient to describe your samples?

Absolutely

Mainly

Not at all

- If not: which terms were missing? Please provide the variable (e.g. "sample type") and the missing term

- Anything else you want to tell us? (free text)

Reference:

Wieczorek; Mareike; Heim, Birgit; Brauser, Alexander; Elger, Kirsten; Baldewein, Linda (2022) FAIR WISH D3 - Assisting and Assessing User application of the FAIR SAMPLES Template. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377904>